

CURRENT ROOT CANAL IRRIGATION TREND AMONG DENTIST IN INDIA -A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Irrigation is often regarded as the most important part of endodontic treatment, in particular for the eradication of root canal microbes. During and following instrumentation, irrigating solutions facilitate the killing and removal of microorganisms, necrotic and inflamed tissue and dentine debris. Hence we conducted the survey to ascertain the current trends in irrigation among dental practitioners in India.

Material & Methodology: An online-based questionnaire survey was conducted and total 210 dentists were participated. For collection of data a pre-structured, close ended questionnaire consisting of 17 questions were shared. Statistical analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics in the SPSS software.

Results: Our data indicate that most commonly used irrigation solution was normal saline (55.2%) and sodium hypochlorite (29.5%) at a concentration of 2.6-4.0%. 66.7% percent of respondents aim to remove the smear layer during endodontic treatment. 82.9% dentist change irrigant based on the pulp or periapical diagnosis.

Conclusion: The dental practitioners must update themselves in view of recent advancements in this regard, and perform the irrigation procedures more meticulously.

Key words: Irrigation, root canal irrigants, smear layer, sodium hypochlorite.

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Introduction-

Irrigation is a key part of successful root canal treatment as it fulfils several important mechanical, chemical and (micro) biological functions. Irrigation is also the only way to impact those areas of the root canal wall that are not touched by mechanical instrumentation¹. Irrigation is often regarded as the most important part of endodontic treatment, in particular for the eradication of root canal microbes. During and following instrumentation, irrigating solutions facilitate the killing and removal of microorganisms, necrotic and inflamed tissue and dentine debris. ² Irrigation reduces friction between the instrument and dentine, improves the cutting effectiveness of the files, dissolves tissue, and cools the file and tooth especially during the use of ultrasonic energy. Irrigation may prevent packing of the hard and soft tissue into the apical root canal and extrusion of planktonic and biofilm bacteria out into the periapical tissues.³

Before using instruments and during the operation, irrigation is used as a pre-instrumentation phase.⁴ The ideal root canal irrigant has been described by Zehnder ,as

being systemically nontoxic, noncaustic to periodontal tissues, having little potential to cause an anaphylactic reaction, possessing a broad antimicrobial spectrum, capable of dissolving necrotic pulp tissue, inactivating endotoxins, and either preventing the formation of a smear layer or dissolving it once it has formed.⁵

Root canal irrigation solutions provide lubrication and a wide antibacterial effect against diverse species established in biofilms, as well as deactivation of bacterial endotoxin in the root canal. They, physically, enable the irrigant to flow through the root canal. Although water and normal saline are compatible, instrument debridement alone is inadequate to remove pulp tissue, debris, and bacterial biofilm from the root canal. Antibacterial medications, such as sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), chlorhexidine gluconate (CHX), EDTA, and a combination of doxycycline, were used as irrigants to test their effectiveness.⁶ Irrigation's effectiveness and safety are determined by the method of supply.

Different means of delivery are used for root canal irrigation, from traditional

syringeneedle delivery to various machine-driven systems, including automatic pumps, vibrating tips and sonic or ultrasonic energy. The conventional needle syringe method of irrigant delivery remains to be widely employed technique during endodontic therapy. Although for performing irrigation, syringes of varying capacities ranging from 1-20 ml was found to be used, the syringe capacity of 5-ml has been advocated as an appropriate compromise between ease of use and less-frequent refilling. A 5 ml syringe even if combined with finer gauge needles can efficiently reach a flow rate of about 0.20-0.25 mL/s. Due to various cross chemical reactions between the irrigants used; separate syringes must be employed to deliver different solutions. In recent years, the use of finer diameter needles (28, 30,31G) has been insisted because they can reach even up to apical third. Hence, small30-gauge side-vented needles were found to deliver the irrigant effectively.⁷ The goal of the various ways to improve irrigation is to secure optimal spreading of the irrigants throughout the root canal system for more predictable cleaning of the difficult-to-reach areas.

Some of the aspects of irrigation cited above have recently changed due to extensive research in the area. Surveys in different

parts of the world have been carried out with the aim of assessing the understanding as well as clinical practice preferences regarding irrigation. So the present survey was conducted to ascertain the current trends in irrigation among dental practitioners in India.

Material and methodology

Study design and study area

A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted among the dentist of India, for 3 months during the period of July to September 2022.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for the conduction of the research was obtained from institutional ethical committee of People's Dental academy, Bhopal, India.

Study Population and Data collection

The current study was an online-based questionnaire survey. A total of 210 dentists including Private practitioner, Academician, Post graduate students and interns included in the survey using convenience sampling technique. Dentist who agreed to give their consent were included in the study. The

Google survey app was used to construct the questionnaire and valid link was shared through social media. For collection of data a pre-structured, close ended questionnaire consisting of 17 questions were shared. Most of the questions were pretested taken from previous studies and used with minor modifications. A pilot study was done using 10% of sample size to confirm validity and reliability of remaining questions.

The questionnaire was formulated which comprised of two parts: The first portion included the questions related to the demographic information of participants, such as age, gender, year of experience. Age was further subdivided into four groups i.e. from 20-25, 26-30, 30-35, 36-40 and more than 40 years. Participant's affiliation was categorized as Intern, post graduate, academician, private practitioner, both Clinician and academician and their year of experience was also categorized into four groups less than 5, 5-10, 11-20 and > 20 years. The second portion of the questionnaire comprised 13 questions to assess the current root canal irrigation trend among dentist in India.

Statistical analysis-

Data were entered in Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and statistical analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 25.0, (IBM SPSS, Inc. Chicago, Illinois).

Results-

There were 210 respondents out of 500; obtaining a response rate of 42.0%. In the present study 29.5% Male and 70.5% Females were participated. The distribution of respondents according to age was as follows. 31.4% of participants were in the age range of 20 to 25 years. 43.8% of participants were in the age range of 26 to 30 years. 14.3% of participants were in the age range of 30 to 35 years, 2.9% of participants were in the range of 36 to 40 years, 7.6% of participants were above the age of 40 years. According to Affiliation 24.8% Participants were Interns, 29.5% of participants were Post Graduates, 2.9% were Academician, 27.6% were Clinician and 15.2% of participants were Both academician as well as clinician. The distribution of respondents according to year of professional experience is such that around 75.2% of dentists had 0-5 years of experience,

15.2% dentists had 5-10 years of experience, about 6.7% of them had more than 11-20 years of experience and only 2.9% of the

practitioners had more than 20 years of experience. **(Figure 1)**

Figure 1- Frequency distribution of study participants (n=210)

When asked about the most preferred needle gauge for irrigation, majority of dentist 42.9% prefer 27 gauge needle, 23.8% prefer 23 gauge needle, 18.1% prefer 25 gauge needle and 15.2% prefer 30 gauge needle. About the most preferred type of needle used for irrigation, majority of dentist 48.6% prefer Open ended beveled type of needle, 31.4% prefer closed ended side vented type of needle, 12.4% prefer Open ended flat needle and 7.6% prefer closed ended double vented type of needle. **(Table1)**

Our results revealed that most frequent method used to activate irrigant in the apical third region of root was Endovac method (45%), followed by ultrasonic method (23%), sonic method (15%), Manual Dynamic agitation method (9%) and 8% dentist reported none of above method were used. **(Figure 2)**

When asked about final irrigation solution after completing BMP (Bio mechanical preparation). Most of the dentist (55.2%) prefer normal saline. 29.5% dentist prefer

Sodium hypochloride, 7.6% prefer MTAD (mixture of Chlorhexidine, 6.7% prefer EDTA tetracycline, acid and detergent). (Figure 3) (Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) and only

Table 1- distribution of responses regarding current root canal irrigation trends (n=210)

Questions with options	Responses				
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Which needle gauge would you prefer for irrigation?(23 gauge/25 gauge/27 gauge/30 gauge)	23.8%	18.1%	42.9%	15.2%	-
Which type of needle you are using for irrigation?(Open ended flat beveled/Open ended beveled/Closed ended side vented/Closed ended double ended/Closed ended multi-vented)	12.4%	48.6%	31.4%	7.6%	
Concentration Of sodium hypochlorite you are using for irrigation? (< 1.5 %/1.6 – 2.5 %/2.6 – 4.0 %/4.1 – 5.0 %/>5 %)	21%	21%	27.6%	17.1%	13.3%
Which concentration of chlorhexidine do you primarily use?(0.17%/0.18%–1.9%/2.0%/>2.0%/I do not use chlorhexidine)	13.3%	9.5%	51.4%	2.9%	22.9%
Do you routinely aim to remove the smear layer?(Yes./No)	66.7%	33.3%			
Which irrigant would you primarily use in previous endodontically treated tooth?(Sodium hypochlorite/Chlorhexidine/Saline /Sterile water/None)	41.0%	36.2%	21.0%	2.9%	0%
With evidence of periapical lesion what irrigant would you primarily choose?(Sodium hypochlorite/Chlorhexidine/Saline /Sterile water/None)	30.5%	35.2%	33.3%	0%	
Do you change irrigant based on the pulp or periapical diagnosis?(Yes/No)	82.9%	17.1%			
Do you change the concentration of your preferred irrigation solution based on periapical diagnosis?(Yes/No)	75.2%	24.8%			

When asked about the concentration of sodium hypochlorite used for irrigation, Most of the dentist (27.6%) reported that they prefer 2.6-4.0 % and 21 % dentist prefer <1.5% and 1.6-2.5% concentration of sodium hypochloride.17.1% dentist prefer 4.1-5.0% and 13.3% prefer more than 5% of concentration. When asked about the concentration of Chlorhexidine used

primarily. Most of the dentist(51.4%) used 2.0% concentration, 22.9% dentist did not use Chlorhexidine, 13.3% dentist used 0.17 % concentration.9.5% of the dentist used 0.18-1.9% Chlorhexidine, 2.9% dentist prefer > 2.0% concentration of the Chlorhexidine. (Table1)

When questioned regarding the removal of smear layer 66.7% of dentist routinely aimed to remove smear layer and 33.3% of dentist did not remove smear layer. **(Table1)**

Our results revealed that majority of respondents,77% used EDTA irrigation solution for the removal of smear layer,20% reported that they did not use any irrigation solution,2% reported MDAD and 1% reported citric acid.**(Figure 4)** about the amount of irrigant frequently employed most of the dentist (51.4%) reported 5-10ml,22.9% reported 2.5ml,19% dentist reported 0.5ml and 6.7% reported more than 10ml.**(Figure 5)**

Our results revealed that majority of respondents, 41.0% used sodium hypochlorite irrigation solution in previous

endodontically treated tooth.36.2% dentist used Chlorhexidine, 21 % dentist used saline,1.9% dentist used sterile water. When questioned regarding the preference of irrigant for the tooth having the evidence of periapical lesion.35.2% dentist preferred Chlorhexidine, 33.3% dentist preferred saline, 30.5% preferred Sodium hypochlorite and 1.0% preferred sterile water.

Our research revealed that 82.9% dentist change irrigant based on pulp or periapical diagnosis and 17.1 % did not change. Regarding the concentration 75.2% dentist change the concentration of irrigation solution based on periapical diagnosis and 24.8% dentist did not change. **(Table 1)**

Figure 3- Most commonly used final irrigating solution after completing BMP

Figure 4- Most frequently used irrigating solution for the removal smear layer

Figure 5- Most Frequently employed amount of irrigant per canal

Discussion-

This survey aimed to collect data from practicing dentists in India regarding the various trends followed in irrigation during root canal treatment. Our survey was based on the survey employed by Gopikrishna et al.⁸ the positive response rate in our survey was 42%. While this was 33.23% in the study conducted by Gopikrishna et al. during 2013⁸ while this was 96% in the study conducted by Koppolu M et al during 2016.⁹

The classical way of irrigating the root canal is with a syringe and needle. When carefully used, needle irrigation can be effective and sufficient. Small size 27-gauge or preferably 30-gauge needles should be used to gain access to the apical canal.¹ In the present study most of the respondents preferred 27 gauge needle with Open ended beveled design for syringe irrigation. 26 gauge needle with single-beveled tip design was most commonly used in the study conducted by Koppolu M et al.⁹ Different irrigation needle gauges and designs may affect the efficacy of endodontic irrigation in cleaning the root canal. A study by Guerreiro-Tanomaru et al¹⁰ concluded that the 30 gauge needles with side and apical opening promoted better apical cleaning at all stages of root canal widening. Kahn et al¹¹ reported that side-vented closed-end needles

were more efficacious than conventional needles in clearing red food dye from root canals.

New equipment introduced to root canal irrigation includes the EndoActivator¹², various ultrasonic and sonic devices where the irrigant is directed into the canal through the vibrating tip. Several reports have indicated that the various devices may facilitate irrigation, particularly in the difficult-to-reach areas of the canals, such as fins and isthmuses and in large lateral canals.¹³ In the present study most of the respondents preferred Endovac(45%) and Ultrasonic (23%).

In the present study most frequently used final irrigation solution after BMP was normal saline (55.2%) and sodium hypochlorite (29.5%) with concentration of 2.6 – 4.0 % which is similar with the findings of survey conducted by Koppolu M et al⁹ but study conducted by Sedani S et al¹⁴ reported that Sodium hypochlorite in the concentration of (0.5- 5.25%) was used for irrigation by 69(82.2%) practitioners. Similar results were obtained in the study conducted by Zuhair et al.¹⁵ and Gade et al.¹⁶ in which sodium hypochlorite was most employed and is

current irrigating solution of choice. The probable reason for such a finding in present study could be the ease of availability of normal saline, its cost effectiveness as opposed to other effective irrigants and the established fact that normal saline is least harmful to the oral hard and soft tissues.

In present study most of the respondent (66.7%) aimed to remove smears layer using EDTA (77%) irrigation solution. Koppolu M et al⁹ reported 59.7% of the respondents in the study aimed to remove smear layer, 47.2% use saline as primary irrigation solution. The smear layer should be removed as it contains microbes and microbial antigens baked into it during instrumentation of the necrotic, infected root canal. EDTA only affects the inorganic part of dentine and smear layer (hydroxyapatite) and complete removal of the smear layer can only be achieved when NaOCl has been used before the final rinse with EDTA.^{17,18}

82.9% of respondents in our study stated that their choice of irrigant might change on the basis of pulpal and periapical diagnosis. Most of the respondent prefer sodium hypochloride irrigant in previous endodontically treated tooth. The primary irrigant employed for teeth with the radiographic evidence of peri- apical lesion

was Chlorhexidine (35.2%). Gopikrishna et al.⁸ reported similar findings.

Conclusion

This study mostly focuses on evaluating the current root canal irrigation trends. Present study revealed that most of the irrigation trends followed by the respondents were based on the ease of availability and cost effectiveness of material. The dental practitioners must update themselves in view of recent advancements in this regard, and perform the irrigation procedures more meticulously.

Limitation

The present study has a response rate of 42% which is considered lower to be illustrative for the general practitioners across the country. The larger sample size may better provide the true picture. Further studies covering all the dental practitioners registered under Dental Council of India should be surveyed to regulate and improve the quality of endodontic treatment in dental practice.

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